

ENGLISH IN THE LANGUAGE FRENCH APPROPRIATION WORDS**Khamidova Nargiza Yusufovna**

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Abstract :

In the article, French of the language English to the language Effect in detail we learn Article English in the language French the language mastered words wide scope, and their English language vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation affect learning. The article French of the language English to the language significant Effect showed historical events, that's it including the Norman Conquest in the 1066 period image with begins. Then, today in the day English speech often occurring part has been main French mastered words seeing will be released. In the article, French from the language received to use a dictionary English to the dictionary effect in detail analysis including French from the language mastered food, fashion, sports, politics such as the main lexicon of categories description. Also, different methods see comes out. The article is also in French from the language received appropriation of words English language grammar influence, including French from the language mastered different grammar structures, for example, voice, verb tenses, as well as English in the language grammar structures of adaptation different methods and others description, seeing will be released.

Keywords: French from the language mastered words, English language, pronunciation, phonetics, phonology, vocabulary, grammar, cultural effect.

Login.

In the world, the most widespread language has been the English language a lot of centuries of development, and many languages effect under formed. English to the

language significant effect showed from languages one French is a language It's French-language English to culture take In 1066, the Normans entered by England pressing get such as historical factors reason was English and French of languages next mutual effect French words and of phrases English to the language a lot amount to be assimilated take came. In the article we are French from the language mastered of words English of the language pronunciation the effect, they wide applied fields, as well as French from the language received of sounds description and their phonetic and phonological effect seeing we go out We are also English in the language the most a lot applied French their words spreading and English of the language vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation effect seeing we go out This of the article purpose English in the language French appropriation words analysis make, their English of the language pronunciation and to the dictionary The influence is also French appropriation words English in the language speaker countries culture and society in formation how important role that he played is to show. French language English language in history is the most impressive language one is considered and the French language received debts still English speech different aspects to find can.

Books analysis and methodology.

English in the language French appropriation words analysis to do for I literary and empirical of approaches from the combination I used it. A literary approach to the English language history and other languages, that's it including the French language with mutual connection with depends on literature to learn own into takes. Also, we are linguistic sources and dictionaries based on English in the language French from the language of acquisitions lexicon and phonetic aspects seeing we went out Empirical approach English in the language French the words learning for phonetic and lexicon analysis methods to use own into takes. I am English in words and French sounds learning from audio recordings I used and French from the language received expressions and the words analysis I did I am also a sociolinguist information analysis to do methods used without English in the language French of appropriation historical,

social and cultural aspects seeing I came out. Methodology linguistic, historical, sociological, and cultural aspects combined interdisciplinary approach based on was. This is the approach to me English in the language French acquisitions wider in context seeing to exit and they are how formed and their English speaking and to culture effect to understand possibility gave.

Results.

Research results that are it showed that French from the language received words in the English language both in pronunciation and vocabulary significant effect shows. French from the language English to the language the most widespread phonetic acquisitions between the French letters " ch " and "j". suitable incoming [ʃ] and [ʒ] sounds there is From this except for [ã], [ɔ], [ɛ], [ə], and [u]. French from the language received other sounds are also identified. Most interesting from the results is French from the language received words. English language dictionary in formation, especially art, cooking, fashion, and jewelry in the fields important role plays From this besides, many French words and expressions English in the language separately to the meaning have and most of the time simpler English equivalents in communication though is used. Research also French appropriations English in a language with deep historical roots have that showed. 1066-1450 years between of England The Normans pressing taken and France and England between next political, social and cultural connections relationship with many French words and phrases English to the language mastered. From this, research that's it showed that the French appropriations present at the time, especially culture and art in the field of English to the language at the entrance continued is doing For example, "haute couture", " cuisine", "a la carte", "fiancé(e)", " déjà vu" and "savoir-faire" French the word and expressions English in the language wide in application continue is doing and they are now more and more expanded is going.

Discussion.

Transferred analyses based on how many conclusions are released can First, French appropriation words English of the language pronunciation significant effect does They are not only new sounds they enter, maybe there is of sounds they also change the pronunciation. Example for, in English in the language word sound [k] at the beginning of French from the language to the [ʃ] sound when assimilated will be replaced. Second, French appropriation words in English of the language It is also noticeable in the vocabulary effect shown. English to the language the most a lot decreased words French the language come in came, especially from 1066 medium of centuries to the end This of words most of the culture, art, fashion, cuisine and of life another aspect with depends being, this France and England between cultural mutually of influence importance shows. Thirdly, French appropriations English in the language speaker's countries culture in formation important role plays. Modern English in the language usually acceptance done many words French from the language come came out This is English in the language speaker's countries music, literature, cinema, and of culture, another in the fields own on the contrary found. And Finally, English in the language French in the language appropriations analysis to do not only foreign languages to learn but maybe different countries and nations between cultural connections to understand help also gives. French debts English in the language speaker countries history and of culture important part is present at the time language and of culture development effect in doing continue is doing French appropriations English to the language and English in the language speaker countries to culture significant effect shows. This appropriation of the words learning English language history and his centuries during evolution deeper to understand enable gives English of the language pronunciation analysis from what I did then French from the language received acquisitions English of the language phonetic system in formation important role that he played I found out. This is especially English in the language before there is without /f/, /z/, /θ/, /ð/ and another sound in application it is felt. Besides, French

from the language received doesn't shrink words English to the dictionary big effect showed I found out. English in the language more than 30% of the words French from the language come came out and most of them culture, cuisine, fashion, art, and the science of life different fields very important. Also French appropriation words English of culture formation contribution added I found out. French culture long and too rich history have and his French cuisine, fashion, literature, music, and art as many elements of French appropriation words through English culture indispensable to the part turned So doing research results that's it shows that French appropriation words in English language and English in the language speaker countries culture for big important have. They are not only English of the language phonetic system and dictionary of the composition formation contribution added maybe English of culture is also important in formation role played.

Summary.

Summary instead of that's it to say must be English language and of culture in formation French appropriation words important role played. They are English language new words and expressions with filling it word wealth expanded. From this, the English language pronunciation effect showed and to him himself special great manuscript gave French from the language mastered words the speakers of another language for the English language to learn for difficulty shows them. English culture indispensable part being his history and development better to understand possibility gives In general in fact, English in the language French don't be selfish words today's in the day important role while playing continue is doing and life and culture new in the fields appear in becoming continue from doing stopped no them learning and to understand not only English language, perhaps more widely - English in the language speaker countries culture and history is better to understand help gives.

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